

THE ROLE OF EMOTIONAL ENGAGEMENT IN LEARNING LANGUAGE: INNOVATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract:

In this article the impact of emotional engagement on language acquisition and innovative methods to teach a foreign language are explored. Additionally, the article highlights A.J. Hoge's Effortless English method, which emphasizes learning through emotionally engaging contexts to boost student confidence and natural language use. By enhancing emotional connections to the material, these innovative techniques, given below, promote more active participation and deeper comprehension, leading to improved long-term language retention. Through these innovative methods, the teaching of a foreign language can be transformed into a more pleasant and effective experience, offering students not only cognitive rewards but also a lasting emotional connection to the language.

Key words: kin-esthetic learners, emotional engagement, belief, The direct method, Audio-lingual method, Suggestopedia, Communicative language teaching (CLT), Task-based language learning, The Lexical Syllabus, CLIL, Total physical response, Flipped classroom.

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In any fields of language education, emotional engagement is considered as the key factor to reinforce learning process involving memorization, attention, perception and problem solving. While traditional methods center on grammar drills and only memorization of new words, modern researches show that the influence of emotion plays a critical role in how learners obtain effective skills in learning languages. Emotion is the connection for learners to feel the learning process and language in an effective way. Motivation, confidence and powerful memory are cultivated by good emotional state of learners. According to A.J. Hoge's research which is enlightened in his book namely "Effortless English", at the primary stage of learning languages learners gain either pleasant emotion or hateful emotion by utilizing various types of methods. As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, the demand for innovative ways of teaching foreign languages grows significantly, and which pushes educators to investigate new approaches to appeal learners in teaching process. Traditional methods have nearly killed the enthusiasm of most language learners who found traditional approaches completely lifeless and complicated. The main purpose of this article is to demonstrate how important the place of emotional engagement in learning languages and explore innovative methods which is believed as great bridge of teaching languages successfully in modern world.

Neuro-linguistic Programming, a successful psychology system, developed by Richard Bandler and John Grinder, focuses on the psychology of the success, high-performance and motivation, which provides us with accurate experiments related to emotion. According to Grinder and Bandler's research, happy, motivated and energetic people can actually learn better. And they can perform themselves successfully in any field of life. During the learning process, happy learners gain more data and spend shorter time to learning a target topic rather than bored learners. When people feel tiredness, nervousness, stress or broadness, the

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brain functions slowly and struggles to remember information. What do you think? Why do learners feel boredom or nervousness? A.V. Hugo mentioned that in schools, students are practiced to be passive, not active. They sit in chairs, in rows. Sitting for a long time is a low-energy activity. The longer you sit, the more your energy drops and you lose your concentration.

Nearly all of the learners are considered kinesthetic learners who interact with objects through movements and this type of students prefers doing rather than listening to the topic. When they are able to move during the learning process, they can enjoy and their results will be better. Inactivity leads to inactive mind that prolongs the learning process.

Beside the inactivity, there are other factors to effect the emotional state of learners. If learners are embarrassed during the lesson because of their correction by a teacher, they feel more nervous and they try to avoid using that language in real life. Making a mistake is a normal situation, but due to the correction by educators, learners identify that making a mistake makes them shy among peers or classmates. It is so painful for them. If teachers allow learners to realize their own mistakes, this kind of trauma about language does not appear in learner's mind, which let learners absorb the subject successfully.

Moreover, there is something in education, which provides language learners with no benefits: tests and grades. Most learners focus on the tests or grades and they feel if they know the true answer of a question, they know a target language. If they fail it or take a bad grade, they think they are terrible at language learning. And their motivation drops to learn a language. However, learning language is not a test or a grade, it is skill, competence that is combination of ability, skill and knowledge. Therefore, the influence of emotional engagement in learning language can alter the perspective of learners.

To enhance the belief of learners toward a target language, utilizing the relevant methods in teaching is crucial, while traditional approaches are becoming frumpish. At schools Grammar-translation method is valued as a universal, academic and complex way of teaching, even though this approach is too difficult and monotonous for learners. Because this method mostly uses textbooks, lectures, notes and tests.

Graham (1994) investigated the common attributions toward student's success and failure:

- Ability
- Effort
- Task difficulty
- Luck
- Mood
- Help from others

Of course, beside these attributions, the approaches, methods and techniques used in conducting the lesson have a big role in the bright prospective life of learners. And nowadays trying to find an interactive and innovative way of teaching is being in the central part of educator's mind. There are several types of innovative methods which are:

1. The direct method
2. Audio-lingual method
3. Suggestopedia
4. Communicative language teaching (CLT)
5. Task-based language learning
6. The Lexical Syllabus
7. CLIL
8. Total physical response.
9. Flipped classroom

1. The direct method. It is also called natural method and established in England around 1900, as well as, it was adapted by key international schools such as In lingual in 1970s.

This method was developed as a response to the Grammar-Translation method. In this approach learners absorb a knowledge in a foreign language in the same way as when a first language is learnt.

2. Audio-lingual method. Or army method was developed in the USA during 1940s and 1950s after its emergence was largely impacted by the urgent need for people to learn languages during World War II. It relies on drills and repetition to teach a target language.

3. Suggestopedia. In the 1970s Bulgarian psychotherapist Georgi Lozanov suggested this method that uses suggestion to accelerate learning and reduce psychological barriers that learners may have. Organizing a lesson in nature or other comfortable place can be example for this approach.

4. Communicative language teaching (CLT). The goal of this method is authentic and meaningful communication which involves the integration of different language skills, according to J.C. Richards' point of view. In this method utilizing the communicative meaning is important rather than focusing on explicit learning grammar, vocabulary.

5. Task-based language learning. In this method that focuses on the completion of meaningful task, learners create, produce or design something in class and it involves the 21st century skills of communication, collaboration, creativity and critical thinking.

6. The Lexical Syllabus. It is based on a computer analysis of language which identifies the most common words in the language and their various usages. The syllabus teaches these words broadly in the order of their frequency, and big emphasis is placed on the use of authentic materials.

7. CLIL. Content and Language Integrated Learning – an approach in which students acquire a foreign language while focusing on learning new content knowledge and skills and in the same time they learn a target language. For example, learning about science or about composing in other language.

8. Total physical response. TPR is one of the English teaching approaches and methods developed by Dr. James J Asher. This method attempts to focus attention to encouraging learners to listen and respond to the spoken target language commands of their teachers. In other words, this method is a language teaching method built around the coordination of speech and action, it attempts to teach language through physical activity.

9. Flipped classroom. This teaching approach has popularity because of its communicative-based and learner-centered approach to teaching and learning. Sometimes flipped classroom refers blended classroom that is combination of in-person and distance learning. Learners pre-prepared for the lesson and in the class teacher prepare pre-class instructional materials to stimulate learner's interest, so learners engage in the classroom learning tasks.

Moreover, storytelling method which creates an engaging atmosphere for learners to learn a language as a native language in a natural and meaningful way, connecting vocabulary, grammar, and culture to real-life situations. With this method, learners tell a story about given topics, personal stories, play a role or make a story by means of pictures and they feel a language as a native by using authentic tasks.

In conclusion, emotional engagement is a vital yet often ignored element in the language learning process. By tapping into the emotional connection students have with the material, educators can significantly develop both motivation and retention. Innovative teaching methods have proven effective in creating emotionally engaging experiences that deepen understanding and foster a more enjoyable learning environment. By integrating these methods, educators can not only improve students' language proficiency but also encourage a lasting emotional connection to the language itself. Ultimately, by focusing on emotional engagement alongside cognitive development, educators can alter language learning into a more dynamic, interactive, and successful process.

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